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Appraisal Practices And Employee Performance In Aluminium Manufacturing Firms In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined appraisal practices and employee performance in Aluminium Manufacturing firms in Anambra, State as a case study. The study is to investigate the effect of interpersonal factors on employee job, procedural fairness on employee trust and the effect of feedback on employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.. Relevant literature were reviewed under the following sub heading: conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical review. This study is anchored on Goal Setting Motivation Theory propounded by Locke and Latham (1979). The study adopted descriptive survey design. The study area for this study is of Aluminum manufacturing firms in operating in Anambra State. The research was carried out with the use of primary and secondary source of data. The population of the study consisted 1,957 employees. Sample size consist 376 using statistical formula developed by Borg and Gall 1973. The instruments used for data collection was structured questionnaires Face, content and construct validity was adopted. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the test re-test method and Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using simple percentage analysis to answer the research questions, and multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis. The findings showed that interpersonal factors has a significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction, procedural fairness has a significant positive effect on employee trust and evaluation feedback has a significant positive influence on employee effectiveness in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. The concluded that evidence that appraisal practices had a positive significant effect on employee performance. The study recommended that supervisor and the supervisee is an important contributor to overall employee performance effectiveness; procedural fairness method of appraisal practice should be a pre-requisite for the Management of manufacturing firms as this will assist supervisors and employees to discuss weakness, productivity standards and areas of improvement that enhances productivity through employee trust and organisations should re-evaluate the goals that are set, and also implement constructive feedback in relation to the goals as a way of keeping the workforce motivated and accountable to their goals and this in turn will enhance employee effectiveness.

Keywords: Interpersonal Factors, Procedural Fairness, Feedback and Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

The success of any organisation depends on the quality and characteristics of its employees. The employees become a significant factor in any organisation since they are the heart of the company. Organisations cannot achieve their goals and objectives without the employees. Performance assessment plays a significant role in the success of an organisation in attaining its strategic purpose and boosting the

effectiveness of its working process through ongoing development of individuals' performances and processes, combined with a focus on weak and improvable parts (Michael-Ofre & Opusunju, 2021). Appraisal practice is the periodic evaluation of employee's performance measured against the job's stated or presumed requirements. Appraisal practice is a vital tool to measure the frameworks set by any organisation to its employees. It is utilized to track individual contributions and performances against organisational goals and to identify individual strengths and opportunities for future improvements and assess whether organisational goals are achieved or serves as basis for the company's future planning and development (Daoanis, 2019). Appraisal practices are vital components of a broader set of human resource practices which is the mechanism for evaluating the extent to which each employee's day-to-day performance is linked to the goal established by an organisation (Coutts & Schneider, 2017). Appraisal practice is also known as formal, structural system, and evaluation of employee's relation to their job responsibilities (Wahjono, Marina, Perumal, & Wardhana, (2016). However, the outcome is to discover everything about the employee's current performance at the workplace and then improve their performance level more effectively in the future (Mondy 2019). Consequently, it can benefit the employees, as well as the organisation and the society too (Wahjono et al., 2016).

Interpersonal factors as part of appraisal practice has been linked to employee motivation and effectiveness in service delivery. One of a manager's most important responsibilities is to evaluate an employee's performance. This is a fundamental expectation of everyone in a supervisory position. To determine how much each employee contributes to the accomplishment of business goals and objectives, organisations conduct staff evaluations (Umar, Azu, & Sule, 2023). The main goals are often service provision and profit maximization. It has been discovered that appraisal practice systems can significantly boost organisational productivity, organisational harmony, and organisational standing in its environment (Kariuki, 2017). Kariuki defines appraisal practice as an evaluation of an employee's work performance over a predetermined period. It resembles a report card on a worker's performance over the previous year as seen by their management (Umar, Azu, & Sule, 2023). Employee performance is crucial to accomplishing organisational objectives in every organisation. Therefore, performance evaluation is responsible for every organisation's success. One of the fundamental instruments that encourage employees to be highly productive and engaged at work is the appraisal practice (Bernardin & Wiatrowski, 2020). A critical examination of this might highlight the necessity of encouragement, benefits, development, training, and positive interpersonal relationships in a workplace. However, it is a fact that employees need something to induce them so that they are motivated to work at the best interest of the company. This is indicative of the more strategic approach to Human Resource Management (HRM) policies which seek to connect the aims of the organisation to the performance of the individual. The organisation's key aims, goals and objectives become an embedded part of the process in the performance management and communicated through the appraisal practice process. (Daoanis, 2019). Daoanis defines appraisal practice as "a more limited approach which involves managers making top-down assessment and rating the performance of their subordinates at an annual appraisal meeting".

Appraisal practices data were utilized for managerial decision-making and a number of other objectives, such as administrative choices, employee development, and personnel research. Appraisal practice is regarded as an essential human resource function (Muhammad & Surayya, 2020). Performance evaluation, which can be viewed as a general term covering a variety of activities through which organisations seek to assess employees and develop their competence, enhance performance, and distribute rewards, has reportedly become a part of a more strategic approach to integrating human resource activities and business policies. Anso (2017) confirms that performance evaluation has developed into a tool for fostering organisational growth and professional development.

Appraising the performance of individuals, groups and organisations is a common practice of all societies. In some instances, these appraisals processes are structured and formally sanctioned, in other instances they are an informal and integral part of daily activities according to Foss, (2017). Traditionally it involved documentation and communication of performance between staff members and their supervisors. Currently, the process has been formalized and there is some seriousness that accompanies

the procedures including record keeping for future reference (Kagotho, (2018). According to Ochoti, Maronga & Muathe, (2018) the appraisal practice feedback procedure, the relationship between the supervisor and supervisee as well as the rating accuracy increases the employee performance efficiency. The study identified that if the implementation process has taken appropriately, it has a relatively high influence on the employee performance. Begum, Hossain, & Amzad, (2017) assured that employee performance is determined by factors like accuracy of the rating, its perceived fairness and the communication between the appraiser and the appraisee.

In private sector organisations, performance evaluation plays a vital role in achieving its strategic goal and enhancing the effectiveness of its working process by focusing on weak and improvable sections and continual improvement of employees' performance and procedures. With the introduction of appraisal practice system, employees of private sector organisations became aware of their obligations and make effort to carry them out properly, which increases the productivity and success of the organisation. It has been claimed repeatedly that employees must exhibit reactions during the appraisal practice process in order to favourably affect future behaviour and development; otherwise, the appraisal system will be condemned to failure. In general, this study sees appraisal practice as a method of evaluating the behaviour of employees in the work place including both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of job performance. Performance here refers to the degree of accomplishment of the tasks that make up an individual's job description or schedule. It indicates how well an individual is fulfilling the job demands. Often the term is confused with effort, but performance is always measured in terms of results and not efforts. Therefore, with the help of the appraisal practice one can evaluate, identify gaps, suggest improvements and reward good behaviour as well as outstanding performance of the other party. Based on the drives of appraisal practice schemes, this study is centred on using five (5) human resource management practices- inter-personal factors, procedural fairness, evaluation feedback, rater accuracy/bias and performance based promotion as predictors of appraisal practice.

Statement of the Problem

The nonchalant attitudes of private sector workers towards their duties and responsibilities have become a matter of great concern to the private firm owners, government at all levels and other well-meaning Nigerians. There has been persistent public outcry in the mass media indicting private sector organisations employees for their negative attitude to work which has led to low productivity. Despite the fact that implementing appraisal practice systems has a lot of advantages, results have indicated that the practice of appraisal practice is generally plagued by issues related to the subjective nature of the appraisal practice criteria and the inappropriateness of the criteria used to evaluate employee performance. In the organisations under study, there are significant discrepancies on how employees view the current appraisal practice process relative to fairness, feedback, rater accuracy, and satisfaction. There are significant gaps in empirical studies of employees' perceptions of appraisal practice, especially in the institution under study despite the substantial amount of published work on the topic. It has been established that poor appraisal practice has detrimental impact on employee morale, organisational harmful productivity and organisational social standing.

Extant literature has established that poorly executed appraisal exercises have detrimental input on employee morale, commitment to organisational productivity, organisational harmony and corporate reputation. Several studies have demonstrated that many workers have felt uninspired and disillusioned by the conclusion of their performance evaluation at work. This has raised concerns regarding how performance evaluation is handled in private sector organisations and the methodologies used. As a result, the fundamental issue is still how to conduct performance based appraisal that motivates workers and increases productivity through employee performance. This study is motivated by this difficulty and the back and forth between the relevant literatures. Therefore, it is in the light of this, that the study aims at investigating the potential effect of appraisal practice on employee performance (proxied by employee job satisfaction, employee trust, employee commitment, employee quality service and employee skills) of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria in relation to factors like interpersonal factors, procedural fairness, evaluation feedback, rater accuracy/bias and performance based promotion.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to determine the effect of appraisal practice on employee performance of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:-

1. Assess the effect of interpersonal factors on employee job satisfaction in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.
2. Examine the influence of procedural fairness on employee trust in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.
3. Assess the extent to which evaluation feedback affects employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How do interpersonal factors affect employee job satisfaction of employees in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of procedural fairness on employee trust in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria?
3. To which extent does evaluation feedback affects employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- Ho₁**. Interpersonal factors do not have significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.
- Ho₂** Procedural fairness does not have significant positive influence on employee trust of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.
- Ho₃**. Evaluation feedback does not have significant positive effect on employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

Employee Performance

Performance as a concept lacks a generally accepted definition (Andersen, 2018). Consequently, the concept of Performance has been perceived from different angles. For example, from the perspective of process, performance signifies the process of change from inputs to output with the purpose of realising a specific outcome (Muchinsky 2020). Muchinsky explained that employee performance is a set of workforces` behaviours that could be examined, gauged and evaluated with the achievement on an individual level. Mcconnel (2018) defined employee performance as an accomplishment that can be measured and assessed. Bhatia and Jain (2019) assert that performance could be assessed by some mixture of quality, quantity, time and cost. Worker performance is originally what a worker does or does not do. Scholars (Mathis & Jackson 2019; GÜNGÖR, 2021) notes that performance is connected with quantity and quality of productivity, timelessness of productivity, appearance on the accomplished and efficacy of work attained.

The concept of employee performance in the perspective of the organisation is typically described as the degree to which an individual worker of an organisation impacts to accomplishing the objectives of the organisation (Aydogdu & Asikgil 2018). Aydogdu and his associate were of the view that several parts of performance could be evaluated through work attendance, duties assigned for performance and organisation conduct. Employee performance in the private sector organisation could be brought to fore as the act of discharging duties by the employee workforce as stipulated by the organisation for efficiency in service delivery. It is believed that employees` performance is relatively unique, stable, predictable, determinable and controllable (Idowu, 2017).

Appraisal Practice

Appraisal practice is considered to encourage employees in consequent performance cycle (Heneman, & Wemer, 2019). There is an increase use of appraisal practice process (Dechev, 2018) which is mostly motivated by an organisational need to have an effect on employee' attitude, behaviours, as well as organisational performance too. The outcome is the establishment on objectives that is set at the beginning of the assessment cycle which help employees to bring out their obvious performance goals view, the supervising of performance during the assessment which help the poor performers and also support to provide the high-quality performance in an organisation (Wahjono, et al., 2016). The capacity to achieve these positive outcomes will be in function of the appraisal practice experience. Appraisal practice is one element of the performance management process which involves different measurements throughout the organisations. It is the element which is important if organisation is to take advantage of their most important asset (employees) and gain human capital advantage. Appraisal practice can be regarded as the process of recording and assessing employee's performance for the purpose of drawing conclusions about employees that lead to decisions (Abbas, & Cross 2019). Appraisal practice is an analysis of an employee's recent failures and successes, individual strengths and weaknesses and the suitability for promotion or advance training and time to time evaluation of employee's performance measured against the job's requirements or stated (Mani, 2018). In simple terms, appraisal practice refers to the assessment of employee's productivity in a systematic manner, the productivity being measured against factors such as initiative, job knowledge, supervision, leadership abilities, quality and quantity of output, judgment, cooperation, versatility, health and the like (De Waal, 2018).

Armstrong and Taylor (2018) described appraisal practice as a standard of practices that outline the kind of occupation and regulate the engagement relation in order to induce and maintain the appropriate worker, according to its demand. The most essential purposes of performance appraisal practices are to aid and assist organisations to reach decisions and conclusions on salary, promotions, recognising training requires, conveying feedback and recognition of employee for a job well done (Majumder, 2017; Cheng, 2019). According to Majumder (2017), performance appraisal system has been used as a tool in the process of reward and recognition. Additionally, it was used to evaluate the employee's strengths and development needs. Even though it is expensive to carry out appraisal practice, firms should embrace this exercise as it acts as imperative administrative decisions in particular circumstances, where bonuses, training needs, and promotions are resolved, which will ultimately create occupation inspiration and obligation to the firm (Kadiresan et al., 2015). Appraisal practice was first introduced by Lord and Taylor (1914). As a result, many companies were influenced by Frederick Taylor's "Scientific Management" efforts of the early twentieth century. It is therefore believed that the continued success of each organisation depends on its appraisal practices. Employee performance appraisal is one of the most commonly used management tools. It serves many purposes, improved results and efficiency. Appraisal practice is a formal and organized interaction between a subordinate and supervisor, that regularly takes the method of a periodic interview which can be annually or semi-annually, in which the work performance of the employee is well examined and discussed with a sight of recognizing strengths and weaknesses as well as threats and opportunities for skills development and improvement. A long-term process for evaluating employee's performance would not only be in the interest of the individual but also to the organisation.

Stalz (2019) explains that organisations should look at the content of the appraisal system first and satisfy itself that the appraisal system is well understandable and in order not only to the appraiser but also to the appraisee. He also suggests that the appraisal system should be given to the appraisee who will return it to the appraiser, who then rates the appraisee and returns the form to the appraiser to go through and sign if he/she agrees with the rating. But even if the employee does not agree with his supervisors rating, he/she would give his/her own remark, and still signs the appraisal arrangement. The arrangement then goes to the next senior officer or personnel department or the appraisal committee or the managing director as the case may be where the boss rating is changed, added to, and challenged, but the final appraisal result should be communicated to the appraisee through his/her immediate boss who will later on discuss the

final appraisal result in a post appraisal interview. Marmorina (2018) agreed with Stalz (2019) that the process of appraisal practice starts with the creation of performance standards, followed by communicating principles to the workers because if left to them, would find it extremely difficult to know what is expected of them. This is followed by measurement of actual performance and then compare and contrast the actual performance to the performance standard required and discuss the outcome of the appraisal with the employee and if required, initiate corrective action. Armstrong (2019) describe the role of the performance appraisal as a tool for looking forward to what need to be done by people in the organisation in order to achieve the purpose of the job. Better use of technology skills and attributes in addition will develop both organisational and individual capabilities and reach agreement on areas where performance needs the effectiveness of its employee generating information which influences many of organisations decisions. Annual appraisal practices enable management monitor whether institutional standards, expectations, objectives, delegation of responsibilities and tasks are achieved.

Theoretical Framework

Goal Setting Motivation Theory (1979)

This study is anchored on Goal Setting Motivation Theory propounded by Locke and Latham (1979). Locke and Latham (1979), brought about the goal-setting motivation technique which they considered as not only more effective than other methods but also can be treated as a support for them. In their approach, a goal is defined as an object or aim of an action that is attained within a specific limit of time. One of their core findings is that the highest level of performance and effort is produced when the difficulty level of attaining goals is also very high. The only limit is the ability of the person who tries to attain a goal. The theory expresses that people perform better if a specific difficult goal is set than if they are asked to perform as well as they can (Locke & Latham, 1979). They also showed that performance does not differ among employees regardless of whether goals are assigned to people or if people participate in choosing their own goals. This was explained by the fact that usually the superior that assigns the goal is treated as an authority. Furthermore, the act of assigning a goal means that the superior believes that the subordinate can fulfil that goal. As a result, people become motivated to prove their competencies. However, this study relies on the above theory because it provides a strong link between goal setting, which is a subset of appraisal practice and the performance of employees. The theory asserts that goal setting leads to employees' commitment and job satisfaction.

Performance Appraisal and Employee Performance

Every organisational success is dependent on Employee performance. Committed employees achieve objectives whereas, poor performing employees lead to downfall of an organisation. To develop reliable and unbiased ways of evaluating employees, organisations should focus on key factors that drive employee performance. Evidence of positive association between appraisal practice and employee performance have been recorded in literature include Appiah, (2019) and the confirmation have been registered in both private and public organisations. Empirical findings have cast doubt on whether appraisal practice leads to employee performance. It has been indicated in literature by Brown et al., (2018) that ineffective appraisal practice can be alleviated by human resource functions. However, studies have remained subjective in examining how appraisal practice increases employee performance in private sector firms more (Brown et al., 2018).

Empirical Studies

Empirical studies were reviewed variable by variable base on specific objectives. Umar, Azu, & Sule, (2023) examine the effect of employee appraisal on employee performance in Federal Polytechnic, Mubi. Specific objectives of the study were to find out the impact of employee feedback and evaluation on organisational performance, examine the impact of employees' perceptions of fairness on organisational performance and determine the extent of the effect of correctness of the employees' evaluations on the organisational performance at Federal Polytechnic Mubi, Adamawa State Nigeria. The population of the study was 2003 staff while the sample size was 334 obtained through the use of sample size formula by

Yamani (1964). The data collected for this study was subjected to descriptive statistics and hypotheses were tested using regression statistics with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study revealed that there exist significant and positive influence between perceived feedback and employees' organisational performance. However, employees' perceived accuracy shows insignificant influence on employees' organisational performance meanwhile perception appraisal practices revealed negative significant influence on employees' organisational performance. Therefore, the study recommended that management should ensure that Performance Employee Appraisal (PEA) provide technology feedback that should be fair and satisfactory. Various appraisal method should be introduced to encourage objectivity and eliminate biasedness in the appraisal of employees. The reviewed study is related to the present study as it appears to focus on the issue raised in the study on employee appraisal on employee performance. While the study under review was interested in ascertaining the employee appraisal on employee performance in Federal Polytechnic Mubi in Adamawa State Nigeria, the present study determines the effect of employee appraisal on employee performance of private sector organisation in Anambra State. The two studies also differ in geographical location given that the reviewed study was carried out in Mubi in Adamawa State which is in North East part of Nigeria while this current study will be carried out in Anambra state, which is in the Eastern part of Nigeria. The studies also differs in the research design and population.

Okoli, Ewah, and Chukwu, (2023) explore ways of accelerating employee performance through management by objective among workers in manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. Three specific objectives research questions and hypotheses were formulated with the decomposed variables of the study. This study used a survey research design. The study population was three hundred and thirty-three (333) workers whereas the sample size was one hundred and eight two (182) arrived at using Taro Yamane formula. Data were composed using a self-administered questionnaire from the sample size of workers. The simple random sampling system was applied for the study. Pearson correlation coefficient and simple linear regression were applied for hypotheses testing. In the first hypothesis, the study found that participation exerts moderate influence on employee retention among workers in manufacturing firms ($\beta=0.65$, $t=10.36$, $r^2=0.424$, $F=107.272$, $p<0.01$). Secondly, the test hypothesis found that there is a significant positive correlation connecting goal setting as well as employee job satisfaction among workers in manufacturing firms ($r=0.859$, $n=148$, $p<0.01$). In the third hypothesis, the study found that feedback exerts moderate statistical influence on employee commitment among workers in manufacturing firms ($\beta=0.76$, $t=14.24$, $r^2=0.581$, $F=202.815$, $p<0.01$). The study concludes that for manufacturing firms to increase employee performance, setting and managing objectives is imperative. The research recommended that management needs to slot in employees in its actions so as to dissuade them from leaving the firm. The study also advocated that management needs to incorporate employee contributions when setting the firm's goals to boost employee confidence and achieve job satisfaction.

Mose, (2023) explored performance appraisal regarding employee performance to ascertain the influence of performance evaluation on employee performance in the energy sector. The specific objectives of this study was to look into how goal setting career plans influence workers' effectiveness, determine the extent to which competency-based evaluation influence employees performance, investigate the impact of ongoing feedback through employee achievement and to assess how incentives affect employee performance in Kenya energy sector. The study used explanatory sequential design method. The population was 8820 employees, 11% of total population utilizing a sample size of 801 participant attracted as for all divisions in and to organizations, varying from Senior, middle, and lower-level management employees. Consequently, the researcher used a random sampling technique to collect data from respondents at various levels of management in Kenya's energy sector. Semi-structured questionnaires were used to gather primary data because they allow for open-ended responses from respondents and allow the researcher to easily prepare questions ahead of time to guide the discussion and keep the participants on topic. The collected data was analyzed by use of descriptive statistics and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). In relation to the impact on employee performance of

appraisal practice, the observations suggest that the assessment leads to enhanced productivity in an organization. An effective evaluation model can increase the employees' interest and performance to achieve the specific objectives of the organization. Regarding the influence performance feedback on employee service delivery, the findings showed that effective feedback is crucial to employees to achieve their set objectives. Feedback allows employees to know exactly what is expected of them. The key to the successful empowerment and productivity is effective performance feedback between employees and supervisors. Adequate feedback builds accountability, as staff and supervisors contribute to development goals, skills identification, career development and motivation of employees for enhanced performance. The study concluded that efficient appraisal practices allow employees to express their performance challenges, ideas in achieving individual and company's set objectives. Effective feedback on measuring performance can result in improved productivity of employees.

Ngo, (2023) investigated how university students perceive using ChatGPT for learning, including benefits, barriers, and potential solutions. To determine how students felt about using ChatGPT in their learning, a questionnaire was distributed to 200 students via an online survey, and 30 students participated in semi-structured interviews. The research results showed that, in general, students had a favorable opinion of ChatGPT's application. The benefits of ChatGPT, according to students, included saving time, providing information in various areas, providing personalized tutoring and feedback, and illuminating ideas in writing. Also, several barriers to using ChatGPT were recognized, and some solutions were suggested for improvement of using ChatGPT in education. The most concerning issues for students while using ChatGPT were inability to assess the quality and reliability of sources, inability to cite sources accurately, and inability to replace words and use idioms accurately. To address these concerns, some potential solutions can be implemented; for example, verifying ChatGPT's responses with reliable sources; using ChatGPT as a reference source or a consultant tool; providing guidelines for use; and promoting academic integrity to ensure ethical uses of ChatGPT in an academic context.

Helal, (2022) explored the impact of performance appraisal on employee productivity: the case of the Lebanese retail sector. The research focused on quantitative methodology for collecting data and for evaluating the impact of appraisal practice on the performance of employees in the workplace. Data from primary and secondary sources will be gathered and merged to provide a complete picture of the relationship between 360-degree performance evaluations and employee motivation. The survey had been distributed using google forms over a sample of 100 respondents in Lebanese Companies, and the data had been treated using SPSS statistical tool and the results had been displayed in the form of descriptive and inferential statistics. The results showed a direct relationship between management by objectives, 360 degree appraisal, appraisal practice, and organisational performance.

Sugandha, Aishwarya and Pritesh (2022) determined the effect of performance appraisal on employee motivation using a survey of Faculty responses in different departments of Parul University, Vadodara. The specific objectives of the study includes to understand the relationship between performance appraisal and employee productivity, to establish the extent to which performance appraisal process affects employee productivity and motivation, to determine the extent to which appraisers affect staff motivation and to determine the challenges in appraising employee performance. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population of interest consists of 2000 employees of the university. A sample size of 50 was selected from different departments, age brackets, gender and experience in order to cover maximum diversity in a short amount of time. Data was collection using structured questionnaires. The data was analysed after collecting responses through questionnaire and then it was translated into pie charts and excel tables. The data was then analysed to understand the corelation between employee motivation, employee productivity and performance appraisal. The data was presented using bar charts. Lastly, conclusions were drawn on the basis of the analysis.

Helio, Vimolwan and Syed (2022) examined the relative importance of interpersonal factors and their influence on job satisfaction and gender differences among employees in the hotel industry in Dili, Timor-Leste. A survey of hotel employees was undertaken, yielding a total of 385 respondents. Data were analyzed by using correlation and regression analysis. The hypothesized model explained more of the

variance for the male sample than for the female sample. For both genders, career encouragement is a common factor with a direct effect on job satisfaction. For female employees, mentor support directly predicts job satisfaction. Among male employees, informal network directly influences job satisfaction. This study is the first to examine interpersonal factors and their effect on job satisfaction of hotel employees in Timor-Leste and whether such factors predict job satisfaction differently for males and females. We present the theoretical and practical implications of the role of interpersonal factors on job satisfaction.

Boru (2022) access the determinants of performance appraisal on employee performance in case of Bule Hora University. Descriptive and exploratory research design was used with mixed research approach. Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation and percentage was used. Correlation analysis, regression and ANOVA was used as inferential statistical methods were employed to analyze the data. Probability sampling was used with simple random technique to collect the desired responses. Percentage mean and standard deviation was used to describe the nature of response. Result from correlation analysis using indicates that all four variables like self-evaluation; 360-degree feedback, task-based evaluation and MBO play a significant role and are significantly affecting employee performance. As per the regression analysis competition is the most dominating factor that influences the performance appraisal in the study side the most. All four explored determinants played active role in performance appraisal in the study area. The role of each determinant is essential for effective assessment of the employee. Therefore, the university officials were focus on these four determinants according to their importance in study area. The reviewed study is similar to the present as they focused on performance appraisal on employee performance which are of interest to the present study. However, while study under review investigated *the* performance appraisal on employee performance Bule Hora University in Ethiopia, the current study determines the effect of performance appraisal on employee performance of private sector organisation in Anambra State Nigeria.

Istivani (2022) examined the impact of performance appraisal on employee productivity: The Case of the Lebanese Retail Sector. The research focused on quantitative methodology for collecting data and for evaluating the impact of performance appraisals on the performance of employees in the workplace. Data from primary and secondary sources will be gathered and merged to provide a complete picture of the relationship between 360-degree performance evaluations and employee motivation. The survey had been distributed using Google forms over a sample of 100 respondents in Lebanese Companies, and the data had been treated using SPSS statistical tool and the results had been displayed in the form of descriptive and inferential statistics. The results showed a direct relationship between management by objectives, 360-degree appraisal, performance appraisal, and organisational performance. The reviewed study is similar to the present study given that both of them investigated variables of performance appraisal and employee performance. While study under review examine the impact of performance appraisals on employee Productivity: The Case of the Lebanese Retail Sector, the current study will investigate effect of performance appraisal and employee performance in private sector organisation. The two studies also differ in research design. Geographical location and population of their studies.

Michael-Ofre & Opusunju, (2021) investigated the effect of e-performance appraisal on employee performance in the Presidential Amnesty Programme Office, Abuja, Nigeria. The objective of the study is to specifically assess the effect of the proxies of e-performance appraisal viz. goal setting, e-performance review and feedback on employee performance. The study made use of a survey research design; where primary data were collected from a census sample of 122 management and operational level employees in the presidential amnesty programme office in Abuja. All the questionnaire issued was completed and returned representing a 100% response rate. The questionnaires contained closed-ended questions that were rated on a Likert-5-point Scale of “strongly agree, agree, undecided, strongly disagree and disagree.” The data was then analysed with the Multiple Linear Regression. Arising from the result, the model was significant at 0.000 and the null hypothesis was rejected. It was concluded that the employee performance presidential amnesty programme office in Abuja is affected by e-performance appraisal, however, of the proxies tested, e-performance review is insignificant, while goal setting and feedback are

significant. The study recommends that organisations that seek to increase their employee performance should shift from the traditional performance appraisal system to the e-Performance appraisal system. This is because e-performance appraisal has a positive effect on employee performance. The relationship between the reviewed study and the present study is that they focused on effect of performance appraisal on employee performance. However, they differ in some aspects like population of the study, research design, and geographical scope.

Muriuki, & Wanyoike, (2021) used desk review to find out the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance using training and development as the parameter and based the study on expectancy theory which underpins the construct of performance appraisal and employee performance. From the review of literature carried out, it was discovered that gaps existed in literature regarding the association of performance appraisal and employee performance. It was found out that different scholars have different concepts on performance appraisal in regard to employee performance. The study found that inadequacies in performance appraisals are related to organisation structure context while others are associated with the processes. This study recommends the need to examine the association of performance appraisal and employee performance by incorporating both organisation structures and processes with the focus of increasing employees' commitment and performance. The relationship between the reviewed study and the present study is that they examined performance appraisal and employee performance. However, they differ in some aspects, while Muriuki, & Wanyoike's study examined the training and development of employee performance, the present study will determine the effect of employee performance through training, job performance, feedback, recognition and financial reward.

Rani, and Sagi, (2021) determines the relationship between performance appraisal and job satisfaction among the employees in Coca-Cola beverage industry, the study is Visakhapatnam as study area and 212 data samples were considered. In processing of data SPSS software has been adopted, and statistics like percentage analysis, rank analysis and correlation analysis were considered. The results of this study reveals that where the performance appraisal is more in with individuals in the organisation lead to better working conditions, pay and promotion potential, work relationships, use of skills and abilities, work activities and management policies. This study has similar view with the present study in terms of effect of performance appraisal and job satisfaction and differ in terms of the study location, variables and methodology used.

Fodio and Saidu (2021) determined the effects of promotion on job satisfaction in tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Non-probability random sampling technique and multiple regression analysis were applied and 205 questionnaires were administered to the sample respondents to collect data for the study, the questionnaire was structured based on 5-points Likert scale. A purposive selection of two tertiary institutions was made, one federal institution and one state institution. Result shows that promotion has positive influence on job satisfaction and organisational goal attainment. The study recommends that promotion opportunity should be carried out objectively and offered to competent staff at the right time as that can improve job satisfaction in the work place. The study under review relates to the current study in the sense that both are concerned on how promotion affect job satisfaction. While the study under review looked at the influence of promotion on job satisfaction in tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria, the present study intends to look into the influence of job promotion on employee job satisfaction in private sector organisation in Anambra state Nigeria.

Poljašević, Dragana, Marija (2021) explore the effect of Interpersonal relationship as a factor of job satisfaction which is influenced by multiple internal and external factors. Employee satisfaction or job satisfaction was observed as a dependent variable, while interpersonal relationships are defined as influencing factor, i.e. independent variable. Interpersonal relationships imply establishment of social relations and connections between individuals at work. Interpersonal relationships can be defined as the subjective experience of employee in interaction or connection with another person (colleagues or superiors). Factors such as gender, age, education, work experience and job position are included in the analysis as control variables. Main hypothesis in this paper states that positive interpersonal relationships

have impact on employee satisfaction. The independent variable is divided into three segments, namely: communication and work climate, relationship with superiors and relationship with colleagues. Each segment of interpersonal relationships was separately tested in relation to the dependent variable. The base of this paper is an empirical research conducted in 2019. Based on the survey questionnaire, data from 143 employees in the surveyed company were collected. Data processing was performed on the basis of statistical software for social sciences-SPSS. Descriptive and correlation analysis were applied in the data analysis. All hypotheses tested were confirmed. Testing the hypotheses confirm that there is a statistically significant relationship between observed variables and that there is a moderate positive correlation, which implies that interpersonal relationship is a factor of job satisfaction. Main limitation of this research relates to the observation of relationship between variables in a single business entity. However, the coverage of all employees in the conducted research and the high response rate of employees (82%) provide a good basis for data analysis and giving some general conclusions. Detailed description of research methodology enables its repetition in other organizations.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design because the data were principally primary and the results from the analysis were generalized for the entire population of interest. The study area for this study is of Aluminum manufacturing firms in operating in Anambra State. Anambra is a state in southeastern Nigeria and state was created on 27th August 1991. Anambra state has a common boundary with, Imo State, Enugu state, Kogi state and Delta state. The capital and seat of Anambra is Awka which is in Awka South LGA. Awka is both the state capital and headquarter of Awka South. Anambra. The research was carried out with the use of primary and secondary source of data. The population of the study consisted 1,957 employees identified from Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra. Sample size consist 376 using statistical formula developed by Borg and Gall in 1973. The instruments used for data collection was questionnaire structured with five (5) point modified Likert scale response categories of SA, A, U, D SD with figures attached to each response as follows: 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1. The instrument for the study were face, content and construct validated. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the test re-test method and Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient. They yielded co-efficient values of 0.71 and 0.87 for while the overall reliability coefficient for all the clusters was 0.85. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using simple percentage analysis to answer the research questions, and multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the effect of appraisal practice (Independent variable) on employee performance (Dependent variable).

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

The data generated from the respondents through the administered questionnaire were presented and analyzed. Three hundred and seventy-six (376) were administered to the selected company under study. However, three hundred and forty-nine (349) sets of questionnaire were retrieved showing a rate of 93% which is good for the study. Therefore, the analysis and interpretation of data were based on the returned sets of questionnaire. The first section covered the presentation and analysis of demographic data, the second section covered the analysis of data relevant to the research question followed by testing of hypotheses. Finally, the findings of the study were presented and discussed.

Analysis of Data Related to Research Question

In this section, the data related to the research questions formulated in chapter one were presented and analyzed.

Research Question One: *How do interpersonal factors affect employee job satisfaction of employees in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria?*

Table 1 Response to Research Question One

<i>s/n</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>UD</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>SD</i>
1	My supervisor take my performance throughout the evaluation period rather basing on the relationship I have with him/her.	110 (31.5%)	199 (57%)	9 (2.6%)	23 (6.6%)	8 (2.3%)
2	My supervisor complete the appraisal practice reflecting his/she personal like or dislike towards me.	107 (30.7%)	138 (39.5%)	18 (5.2%)	79 (22.6%)	7 (2%)
3	Measuring employee's contribution to the job rather than employee's behavior/relationship will be more effective on the improvement of employee performance.	72 (20.6%)	158 (45.3%)	15 (4.3%)	65 (18.6%)	39 (11.2%)
4	My supervisor treat me with kindness and show concern about my rights as well as able to suppress personal biasness during performance evaluation process.	126 (36.1%)	116 (33.2%)	29 (8.3%)	46 (13.2%)	32 (9.2%)
5	The appraisal system exists in Aluminum manufacturing firms is fair enough in terms of procedures, outcome received on the basis of performance and treatment of top management with the employees	71 (20.3%)	254 (72.8%)	7 (2%)	5 (1.4%)	12 (3.4%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 above indicates that 110 respondents accounting for 31.5% strongly agreed that their supervisor take their performance throughout the evaluation period rather basing on the relationship they have with him/her in Aluminum manufacturing firms, 199 respondents representing 57% agreed, 9 respondents representing 2.6% were undecided, 23 respondents representing 6.6% disagreed while the remaining 8 respondents accounting for 2.3% strongly disagreed. This implies that the company’s mission has a clear focus on appraisal practice using interpersonal factors. The table above indicates that 107(30.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that their supervisor complete the appraisal practice reflecting his/she personal like or dislike towards them, 138(39.5) respondents agreed, 18(5.2%) were undecided, 79(22.6) disagreed while 7(2.0%) strongly disagreed. This shows that positive interpersonal factors motivates employees and thereby pushed them to improve their services in the company.

The table above also indicates that 20.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that measuring employee's contribution to the job rather than employee's behavior/relationship will be more effective on the improvement of employee performance., 45.3% of the respondent agreed, 4.3% of the respondents were undecided, 18.6% of the respondent disagreed, while the remaining 11.2% strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondent agreed that interpersonal factors with the supervisor should not only be adequate but there should be some element of equity.

The table above further indicates that 36.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that their supervisor treat them with kindness and show concern about their rights as well as able to suppress personal biasness during performance evaluation process, 33.2% of the respondent agreed, 8.3% of the respondent were undecided, 13.2% of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 9.2% strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that employee Job satisfaction build organizational psychology that affect employee behaviour.

The table above indicates that 20.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that appraisal system that exists in Aluminum manufacturing firms is fair enough in terms of procedures, outcome received on the basis of performance and treatment of top management with the employees, 72.8% of the respondent agreed, 2% of the respondents were undecided, 1.4% of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining 3.4% strongly

disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that appraisal system through interpersonal factors is an effective tool in increasing employee performance.

Research Question Two: *What is the influence of procedural fairness on employee trust in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria?*

Table 2 Response to Research Question 2

s/n	Items	SA	A	UD	D	SD
6	Job decisions are made in an unbiased manner	42 (12%)	245 (70.2%)	15 (4.3%)	25 (7.2%)	22 (6.3%)
7	Employee concerns are heard before job decisions are made.	80 (19.4%)	194 (55.6%)	17 (4.9%)	31 (8.9%)	27 (7.7%)
8	To make job decisions, accurate and complete information is collected.	122 (35%)	126 (36.1%)	2 (0.6%)	91 (26.1%)	8 (2.3%)
9	Job decisions are applied consistently across all affected employees.	156 (44.7%)	149 (42.7%)	10 (2.9%)	24 (6.9%)	10 (2.9%)
10	Employees are allowed to challenge or appeal job decisions made by management.	121 (34.7%)	146 (41.8%)	15 (4.3%)	54 (15.5%)	13 (3.7%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 above revealed that 42(12%) respondents strongly agreed that job decisions are made in an unbiased manner, 70.2% of the respondents agreed, 4.3% of the respondents were undecided, 7.2% of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 6.3% strongly disagreed. This implies that the sampled organizations believe that procedural fairness is an employee appraisal stigma for achieving specific goals set by the company and dedication to the company. The table above indicates that 80(22.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that employee concerns are heard before job decisions are made in their organisations, 194(55.6) respondents agreed, 17(4.9%) were undecided, 31(8.9) were disagreed while 27(7.7%) strongly disagreed. This shows that the sampled companies believe that procedural fairness are one of important part of employee appraisal in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria that affect employee trust.

Table 2 above further indicates that 122 respondents accounting for 35% strongly agreed that before their organisations make job decisions, accurate and complete information are collected, 126 respondents representing 36.1% agreed, 2 respondents representing 0.6% were undecided, 91 respondents representing 26.1% disagreed while the remaining 8 respondents accounting for 2.3% strongly disagreed. This implies that employees accept that use procedural fairness in dealing with the issues concerning their employee during appraisal practice period which affect employee trust positively. The table above shows that 156(44.7%) respondents strongly agreed that job decisions are applied consistently across all affected employees, 42.7% of the respondents agreed, 2.9% of the respondents were undecided, 6.9% of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 2.9% strongly disagreed. This implies that the sampled organizations apply procedural fairness on issues concerning their employees irrespective of who is involved. The table above indicates that 121(34.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that employees are allowed to challenge or appeal job decisions made by management, 146(41.8) respondents agreed, 15(4.3%) were undecided, 54(15.5) were disagreed while 13(3.7%) strongly disagreed. This shows that the sampled organizations through procedural fairness challenged their employees to appeal job decisions made by management and enhances employee performance and effectiveness on their job because of the trust they had with their organisations.

Research Question Three: *To which extent does evaluation feedback affects employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria?*

Table 3 Response to Research Question 3

<i>s/n</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>UD</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>SD</i>
11	The performance evaluation system provides effective feedback	59 (16.9%)	257 (73.6%)	17 (4.9%)	11 (3.2%)	5 (1.4%)
12	There are discussions between my supervisor and myself during performance assessment	178 (51%)	142 (40.7%)	8 (2.3%)		6 (1.7%)
13	The organization provides appraisal practice feedback annually	61 (17.5%)	179 (51.3%)	18 (5.2%)	66 (18.9%)	25 (7.2%)
14	The organization performance feedback is communicated through electronic mode	81 (23.2%)	164 (47%)	17 (4.9%)	66 (18.9%)	21 (6%)
15	Feedback is not part of appraisal practice	79 (22.6%)	27 (7.7%)	34 (9.7%)	43 (12.3%)	166 (47.6%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 3 above shows that 59 (16.9%) respondents strongly agreed that performance evaluation system provides effective feedback, 73.6% of the respondents agreed, 4.9% of the respondents were undecided, 3.2% of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 1.4% strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that evaluation feedback is very important in motivating employee commitment and raising their performance. Table 4.2.3 above also indicates that 178 respondents accounting for 51% strongly agreed and satisfied that there are discussions between their supervisor and themselves during performance assessment, 142 respondents representing 40.7% agreed, 8 respondents representing 2.3% were undecided, 15 respondents representing 4.3% disagreed while the remaining 6 respondents accounting for 1.7% strongly disagreed. This implies that evaluation feedback has an extraordinary feeling of belonging from employees in the workplace and it in turn increases employee commitment and performance of the organisation. The table above indicates that 61(17.5%) respondents strongly agreed that organisations provide appraisal practice feedback annually, 51.3% of the respondents agreed, 5.2% of the respondents were undecided, 18.9% of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 7.2% strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that evaluation feedback is one of basic tools for any successful organizations as it make employees committed to their job knowing fully well that they would be appraised and rated based on the outcome of the appraisal.

Table 4.2.3 above further indicates that 81 respondents accounting for 22.6% strongly agreed that their organisational performance feedback is communicated through electronic mode, 164 respondents representing 47% agreed, 17 respondents representing 4.9% were undecided, 66 respondents representing 18.9% disagreed while the remaining 21 respondents accounting for 6.0% strongly disagreed. This implies that the employees of the sampled organisation support that performance feedback should communicated through electronic mode. The table above indicates that 34(9.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that feedback is not part of appraisal practice, 27(7.7%) respondents agreed, 79(22.6%) were undecided, 43(12.3) were disagreed while 166(47.6) strongly disagreed. This show that the employees of the sampled organisations believe that evaluation feedback does not contain negative feelings rather it increases employee commitment.

Test of Hypotheses

This study tested the three hypotheses earlier formulated in chapter one using the t value and probability value in the regression coefficients outcome. The table is presented below:

Table 4 Coefficient of the Regression Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	22.006	2.618		8.405	.000
Interpersonal factors (IPF)	.143	.056	.135	2.533	.012
Procedural fairness (PRF)	.144	.057	.137	2.509	.013
Evaluation feedback (EVF)	.069	.059	.063	2.175	.007
Rater accuracy/bias (RAB)	.067	.072	.050	4.928	.000
Performance based promotion	.058	.080	.047	4.818	.009

- a. **Dependent Variable: employee performance**
- b. **Source: SPSS Version 21.0**

4.4.1 Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: Interpersonal factors do not have significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Hi: Interpersonal factors have significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Table 4.4.1 indicates that Interpersonal factors recorded a t-value of 2.533 with an alpha value of 0.012 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, Interpersonal factors have significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: Procedural fairness does not have significant positive influence on employee trust of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Hi: Procedural fairness have significant positive influence on employee trust of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Procedural fairness has a t-value of 2.509 with a probability value of 0.013 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Since threshold, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. Hence, Procedural fairness have significant positive influence on employee trust of Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho: Evaluation feedback does not have significant positive effect on employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Hi: Evaluation feedback have significant positive effect on employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Evaluation feedback recorded a t-value of 2.175 and a probability value of 0.07 which is within the acceptable threshold. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis; hence Evaluation feedback have significant positive effect on employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The study examines appraisal practice and employee performance of selected Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. The data generated were analyzed using multiple regression analysis and the result shows that:-

1. Interpersonal factors (IPF) has a significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.
2. Procedural fairness (PRF) has a significant positive effect on employee trust in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

3. Evaluation feedback has a significant positive influence on employee effectiveness of selected employee commitment in Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Different scholars have different concepts on appraisal practice in regard to employee performance and different employees from various organizations perceive performance appraisal differently. This study examines appraisal practice and employee performance of selected Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. The data generated were analyzed using multiple regression analysis and the result shows that the explanatory variables of appraisal factors (inter-personal factors, procedural fairness, and evaluation feedback) has a significant positive effect on employee performance of selected Aluminum manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. Therefore there is conclusive evidence that performance appraisal had significant influence on employee performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. The study recommends that establishing perfect and well-structured interpersonal relationship between the supervisor and the supervisee is an important contributor to overall employee performance effectiveness.
2. The study recommended that procedural fairness method of appraisal practice should be a pre-requisite for the Management of manufacturing firms as this will assist supervisors and employees to discuss weakness, productivity standards and areas of improvement that enhances productivity through employee trust
3. The study recommended that organisations should re-evaluate the goals that are set, and also implement constructive feedback in relation to the goals as a way of keeping the workforce motivated and accountable to their goals and this in turn will enhance employee effectiveness.

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